

A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON RISK MANAGEMENT FOR INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

Dr Anil Kumar Mahra

Assistant Professor,

Laxmi Bai Sahuji ,Institute of Management , Jabalpur MP India

Abstract

In today's information technology era, several organizations use automated digital technology and information technology application to develop their business for better maintenance of their operations. The information technology risk management plays a critical role in defending an organization's valuable data and information assets. The main aim of information technology risk management is to protect the digital system from IT-related risk. An effective and efficient risk management process is a significant part of an efficacious information technology security program. A good IT risk management approach should be to protect the organization and its resources to perform their operation, not just its digital assets. Consequently, the risk management process should not be treated primarily as a technical function carried out by the IT experts who operate and manage the IT system, but as an essential management function of the organization. The purpose of this paper is to explore the field of risk management for information technology. The risks of information assets have complex nature; the management of risk of information security is addressed by different approaches. The paper provides a systematic literature review on risk management for information technology. To accomplish this purpose we conducted a Systematic Review of the literature in the popular literature databases. It determined that there are several studies about the methods, exist different approaches about the risk analysis.

KEYWORDS: *Information Technology, Security, Risk Management, Security threat, Risk assessment.*

1. INTRODUCTION:

Today's we are living in the world of everyday virus alerts, mischievous attacks, and the threats of cyber-terrorism, it would be fine to evoke the importance of security requirements [1]. Software security is one of the major concerns that is required to build reliable and quality software systems. In recent years, we have observed several organizations are becoming heavily dependent on information technology and its applications to get more assistance rapidly [2]. The information technology risk management policies, procedures and practices to the responsibilities of creating the background, recognizing, investigating, assessing, discussing, observing and communicating risk. As a result, specific information technology risk analysis method should offer two key benefits. The first benefit is to observe real-world security guidelines and efficiently defending the critical assets of the business organization. The second benefit is to deliver valuable analysis data for upcoming assessment through the improvement of secure information management [3]. However in real world environment, most of organizations do not have proper data about security breaches due to inadequate information or unreported cases. The main reason behind this is the financial constrictions do not have suitable information security strategies and IT risk management approach. For that reason, most of available approaches anticipated to estimate the possibility of arecognized vulnerability of security breach largely on guesswork or rough estimation [16]. In addition, available approaches also use horizontal data with a static time frame in order to identify different types of threats which vary with the course of time [17]. According to reported survey, security breaches infected by new kinds of worms, viruses, Trojans and spyware are increasing over the years for instance; a large public sector body was suffered due to Conficker worm [18]. Moreover, this inaccurate information will lead to wrong decisions on information security measure while wasting time and efforts controlling the wrong things by decision makers. Thus, we are being motivated by above limitations in order to propose

appropriate information security risk analysis method by adopting survival analysis approach. Basically, survival analysis approach provides more dynamic or accurate result with highly concerns about censored information (incomplete) data and time dimension. Moreover, this approach has a capability to process censored information correctly and also able to get rid of from sample biasness. Meanwhile, this approach also can be used to identify which factors have significant impact on the event and forecast the survival probability according to the influence of factors [17].

This paper consists of five sections. The next section discusses the concept of risk management process for information technology in a business organization. The third section describes the systematic literature review process. The fourth section discusses the results and comparative analysis. With the fifth section the paper finally concludes.

2. RISK MANAGEMENT PROCESS:

Risk management is the method that enables IT managers to balance the operational and economic prices of protecting measures and deliver the goods improvements in mission capability by defending the IT systems and data that support their organizations' missions. This method isn't distinctive to the IT environment; so it pervades decision-making to many areas of our daily lives. Take the example of home security, for example. Many people arrange to have home security systems put in and pay a monthly fee to a service supplier to possess these systems monitored for the higher protection of their property. Presumably, the owners have weighed the value of system installation and observance against the worth of their home merchandise and their family's safety, a fundamental "mission" essential. For every organization there is some combination of optimum loss prevention and reasonable cost. The purpose of risk management is to seek out that combination [16, 17]. Simply explicit, risk management seeks to avoid or reduce loss in an organization. Loss implies injury to, denial of access to, or destruction of assets. Information technology risk management approach based on some key points like risk analysis, risk reducing measures, risk monitoring, risk identification. The following figure 1 shows the IT risk management process.

Figure 1 Risk Management Process

3. SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

Systematic Literature Review (SLR) is a method of bibliographic research for assesses and investigates the research that is available for a specific topic or an area of interest in consistent sources of scientific information [4]. In contrast to a conservative literature review, a SLR surveys a severe and well-structured categorization of procedural steps, which guarantee a high scientific value of the results. This procedural structure permits the review can be frequent for any researcher interested in the issue by following the steps set. Consists of three main blocks of activities:

- Planning review
- Conducting the review
- Reporting the review

When planning systematic literature review the determination and possibility of the work is clear. The determination of the study is clearly recognized over the research questions, which are related with the purposes of the SLR. When conducting the SLR, a serious analysis of selected literatures is done with the purpose of answer the research questions. Literatures dealing with review methodology in general, that deal with the management of other risks not considered technical and gray information were not analyzed (exclusion criteria). The empirical studies were identified from the Google Scholar, SCOPUS, Science Direct, ProQuest, ACM Digital Library, IEEE Xplore Digital Library and EBSCO databases.

Figure 2 Systematic Literature Review

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

CRAMM (CCTA Risk Analysis and Management Method) was developed by the CCTA (Central Computer and Telecommunication Agency) in 1985 by UK Government. CRAMM is divided into three stages namely; the first stage is asset identification and valuation, second stage is threat and vulnerability assessment and third stage is selection and recommendation. CRAMM also provides compliance guidance on the new version of BS7799 standard, part two. Basically, CRAMM provides well defined stages which cater for both technical and nontechnical aspects of security. CRAMM utilizes qualitative and quantitative measures [4]. NIST SP 800-30 is part of the SP800 series dedicated to IS and published by National Institute of Standards and Technology. This series includes a methodology for the analysis and MRIS aligned [6], [10]. MAGERIT is an open methodology with widespread use in the Spanish context and mandatory for use in Spanish public administration. It is structured into three parts: method, catalogue of elements and technical guide [10].

Microsoft's Security Management Guide establishes a formal process for the MRIS, allowing companies to operate in the most effective manner with an acceptable level of risk [12]. MEHARI was developed for help managers to do MRIS and reduce the associated risks. Reducing risk involves a prior knowledge of management strategies and business processes in order to optimize the investments in security measures both technical and organizational [7]. ISO 27005:2008 establishes guidelines for the MRIS. It is the complement of the ISO/IEC 27001 and ISO/IEC 27002 standards, which define the need to manage the RIS, without specifying how. It is perceived as formalizing international requirements to be met by a methodology of MRIS. The critics of this standard do not see a real contribution in it. Criticism focuses on that the new standard not delves really into MRIS is merely a declarative framework. Regardless of the controversies, this standard has generally served as a reference and inspiration for the proposed and formulation of others methods for the treatment of RIS [15].

OCTAVE focuses on the study of organizational risks, mainly in aspects related to every day work in organizations [11,12]. One of its peculiarities is that it must be performed by personnel belonging functional units and information technology area. There are: OCTAVE (for large organizations), OCTAVE-S (for small organizations) and OCTAVE Allegro (defined to analyze risks with a greater focus on information assets, as opposed to the approach in information resources).

EBIOS provides a comprehensive methodological approach in accordance with the main international RM standards. Establishes a baseline for the certification of competencies related to RM and is applicable to both, the public and private sectors, small medium and large enterprises in francophone countries [11].

IT Baseline Protection Manual interprets the general proposals of the family ISO 27000 and helps users to implement them in practice with many notes, examples and background knowledge [11]. ARIMA covers more fully the processes of ISO/IEC 27005 not covered with methodologies like CRAMM, EBIOS and OCTAVE. The core is to combine the advantages of such methodologies, leveraging the proven techniques and adapt them to comply with the MRIS process [1]. CORAS. It is a method for MRIS using primarily the interviews with experts. It uses i) the UML for defining models for assets, threats, risks, safeguards; ii) a graphical editor based on Microsoft Visio; iii) a library of reusable cases and iv) a textual representation of graphic language based on XML [13]. COBIT is a framework for the management of Information Technology (IT), as well as support tools that allows to bridge the gap between control requirements, technical issues and business risks. In relation to IS and in particular the management of RIS, COBIT contains a framework called Risk IT consisting of a set of guiding principles for MRIS, Risk IT complements [14], [15]. ISM3. It is a management methodology of maturity of controls of MRIS. It is aligned with quality management ISO 9001 and applied to the ISMS. It establishes different levels associated with the controls in MRIS [16]. The aim is to provide best practices to achieve the highest level. It complies with the requirements of ISO/IEC 27001 and presents other methods [3]. The following table 1 shows the comparative literature analysis on different approaches of risk management for information technology.

Table 1 Comparative analysis of different approaches of risk management for IT

Approach	Reference	Year	Contribution
CRAMM	CCTA [14]	1985	Implemented in three phases for risk management
NIST800-30	Stoneburner et. al. [5]	2002	Provide a guide for the foundation of the developing an effective risk management program
MAGERIT	[6]	2006	Determine the relevant assets for the organization, their inter-relationships and their value i.e. what cost would be caused by their degradation
Microsoft's Security Management Guide	[12]	2006	Provides a guide for n security risk management
Mehari	[7]	2007	Provide a set of tools specifically designed for security management, which comprises a set of managerial actions
ISO 27005:2008	ISO [15]	2008	Provides guidelines for the risk management.
Aurum	Ekelhart et. al. [8]	2009	A methodology for supporting the NIST SP 800-30 risk management standard
OCTAVE	Samy et. al.	2010	Provides study of organizational risks

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5. CONCLUSION

This studies shows the different approaches available for the risk management of information technology but there are few studies related to the efficiency, effectiveness and maturity of the controls, which opening possibilities for future research. The propensity for information technology to fail or not to accomplish to prospects makes imperative the need to manage risk as an integral part of information technology risk management. There are few studies on this subject. There is a little evidence for the existence of ancombined approach to the MRIS that considers both the design of the information system for RIS and the analysis of RIS. This need is being addressed as a research by the European project CORAS. Information technology managers must systematically recognize the value of their IT assets, IT risks at different levels, and the related weaknesses of IT assets to these numerous risks. This understanding of the complete impact of IT risks on the entire business organization and its setting will provide management with a basis for considerable and practical speculation in the IT risk management process.

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